

Insect resistance

Rice resistance to thrips

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The rice thrip *Baliothrips biformis* (Bagnall) sometimes reaches populations of economic significance in India. Thrips infest nursery seedlings and the early transplanted crop; they cause leaves to roll, then turn yellow. The plants wilt in severe cases.

From July to September 1979, thrips incidence was heavy in field nursery seedlings at Coimbatore. Based on the range of symptoms, a visual resistance rating scale was developed:

Damage	Rating scale	Grade
Rolling of terminal 1/3 area of 1st leaf only	1	Highly resistant
Rolling of terminal 1/3 to 1/2 area of 1st and 2d leaves	3	Resistant
Rolling of terminal 1/2 area of 1st, 2d, and 3d leaves; yellowing of leaf tips	5	Moderately resistant
Rolling of entire length of all leaves with pronounced yellowing	7	Susceptible
Complete plant wilting followed by severe yellowing and scorching	9	Highly susceptible

Using the rating scale, 25-day-old seedlings of 66 rice cultivars were screened in the field nursery.

Identified as highly resistant were Balamawee, Suduru Samba, Sinna Sivappu, Thirriisa, H105, and Perunel. The resistance of the first three varieties

to certain brown planthopper biotypes is of practical significance. Nine other varieties that were rated as resistant, and should be useful in resistance breeding programs, were ASD7, B2360-11-3-2-3, Babawee, CO29, IET4786, IR4432-52-6-4, Nira, PTB19, and Sudu Hondarwala. ■

Field reaction of rice cultivars to hispa and leaf folder

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A collection of 334 cultivars was assessed in the field in 1978 kharif for varietal differences in tolerance for rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* and rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*. Fifty-day-old seedlings of the cultivars were transplanted in two lines, each 2.55-m long, at a spacing of 20 × 15 cm. The hispa and leaf folder-damaged leaves on 10 hills of each variety were counted at 40 and 75 days after transplanting, respectively.

None of the tested varieties was completely free from insect attack. For rice hispa, the lowest infestation (5 damaged leaves/10 hills) was on IET4109. Cultivars that had comparatively less damage (fewer than 10 damaged leaves/10 hills) were PR299 A, PR385, PR506, PR515, PR285, PR409, PR520, PR440, IET3578, IET5329, and IET6251. The most severely infested

cultivars (more than 80 damaged leaves/10 hills) included PR274, PR437, and CRM5713-13. CRM5713-13 had the highest damage, 93 leaves/10 hills.

For the rice leaf folder, IET625 1 was the least damaged (16 leaves/10 hills).

The most severely infested cultivars were PR299A, PR515, PR437, PR476, 1870, 1991, CRM5710-8, and CRM5761-1. CRM5761-1 had the highest damage, 96 leaves/10 hills. ■

Deep water

Thailand releases two new deepwater rice varieties

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Thai government officials formally approved the release of RD17 and RD19, new semidwarf rice varieties that are tolerant of water depths up to 1 meter, in December 1979. RD17 was previously known by its experimental line number

BKN6986-66-2 and RD19, as BKN6986-147-2. Both varieties were selected from the cross IR262/Pin Gaew 56, made in 1969 at the Bangkok Rice Experiment Station, with the objective of transferring deepwater tolerance and elongation ability from the Thai floating variety Pin Gaew 56 into progeny of the IR262 plant type. IR262 is a photoperiod insensitive semidwarf line obtained 13 years ago from IRR1.

Early generations were tested for deepwater tolerance at Klong Luang and Huntra Rice Experiment Stations and then selected for uniformity and yield at various rice stations and in farmers' fields in the Central Plain, where flooding